

Kinetics of Chelation of Cobalt(II) with α -Amino- β -indolepropionic Acid

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Kinetics of chelation of cobalt(II) with α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid were studied in the pH range 6.18–7.13 and at 25, 30 and $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$ in 0.1 M KNO_3 . Rate constants for the complex formation of cobalt(II)– α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid complex have been determined by the stopped-flow technique. A new reaction scheme on the basis of complete chelation process, which fits best our kinetic data, has been suggested. Specific rate constants corresponding to the different reactive forms of the ligand have been calculated. Activation parameters corresponding to different specific rate constants have also been determined.

THE reaction of nickel(II) with a large number of bidentate ligands^{1–8} has been studied kinetically.

Unfortunately, very few kinetic studies^{9,10} on the reaction of cobalt(II) with bidentate ligands have been reported. These kinetic studies of nickel(II) with bidentate ligands could be explained on the basis of simple reaction scheme, which however, could not explain complexation of cobalt(II) with α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid.

Review of the literature^{11,12} reveals that such difficulties may be overcome by a detailed examination of chelation process. We have, however, developed a new scheme for cobalt(II)– α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid reaction (on the basis of chelation process). This new scheme is found to fit best our kinetic data.

Experimental

α -Amino- β -indolepropionic acid (L-tryptophan; B.D.H.), 2,6-lutidine (Merck-Schuchardt), bromothymol blue (B.D.H.) and KNO_3 (A.R.) were used. Solution of Co^{II} was prepared from $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck) and standardised by EDTA titration¹³. The ionic strength of all reactions were kept constant at 0.1 M by addition of calculated amounts of KNO_3 . Freshly prepared solution of α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid (4.54×10^{-3} M) was used.

Measurements: Kinetic measurements were made on a Aminco-Morrow stopped-flow spectrophotometer. The driving syringes and reaction chamber were thermostated at 25–35° ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) with the immersion type thermostat (German, model NBE). In the stopped-flow reaction chamber, a solution of Co^{II} ($\sim 10^{-3}$ M) having ionic strength 0.1 M and at the desired pH (adjusted by 0.052 M 2,6-lutidine buffer) was mixed with a solution of α -

amino- β -indolepropionic acid (containing $\sim 10^{-5}$ M bromothymol blue as an indicator) at the same pH and at the same ionic strength. The Co^{II} concentration was taken in excess as compared to ligand to maintain pseudo-first order conditions. There was, however, a slight change in pH (of the order of 0.05 unit) after mixing. The final pH was taken on a Radiometer (model pH M 26, Copenhagen). The pH values reported are those of the reaction mixtures.

The complex formation was monitored by change in the colour of the indicator at 620 nm. Transmittance changes for each run were traced out from the oscilloscope. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k'_{obs}) were calculated from the slope of the semilogarithmic plots of ΔV (change in voltage) vs time.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of the chelation of Co^{II} with α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid were carried out in the pH range 6.18–7.13 and at 25, 30 and $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$ in 0.1 M KNO_3 . The rate equation for cobalt(II)– α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid reaction can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= -\frac{d}{dt}[\text{Co}^{2+}] = -\frac{d}{dt}[\alpha\text{-amino-}\beta\text{-indolepropionic acid}] \\ &= k_{\text{obs}}[\alpha\text{-amino-}\beta\text{-indolepropionic acid}][\text{Co}^{2+}] \\ &= k'_{\text{obs}}[\alpha\text{-amino-}\beta\text{-indolepropionic acid}] \\ &= k'_{\text{obs}}\{[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}] + [\text{HN}^+-\text{O}^-] + [\text{N}^+-\text{O}^-]\} \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

where, $k'_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{obs}}[\text{Co}^{2+}]$ and HN^+-OH , HN^+-O^- and N^+-O^- are diprotonated, monoprotated and deprotonated forms respectively of the α -amino- β -

indolepropionic acid. The values of pseudo-first order rate constants (k'_{obs}) were calculated from the usual semilogarithmic plots of ΔV vs time. The values of second order rate constants ($k_{\text{obs}} = k'_{\text{obs}} / [\text{Co}^{2+}]$) are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS
 $I = 0.1 \text{ M (KNO}_3\text{)}$

(α -Amino- β -indolepropionic acid) = $4.54 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$

[Co ²⁺] × 10 ³ M	Temp. °C	pH	$k_{\text{obs}} (\times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$	
			Experimental	Calculated
4.50	25	6.34	3.81	3.81
4.50	25	6.28	4.23	3.99
4.50	25	6.40	4.23	4.31
4.50	25	6.50	4.36	4.58
4.00	25	6.57	4.48	4.76
4.00	25	6.65	4.76	4.95
4.00	25	6.73	5.02	5.11
4.00	25	6.77	5.44	5.21
3.70	25	6.85	5.20	5.35
3.70	25	6.91	5.44	5.45
4.50	25	6.79	5.20	5.25
4.50	25	6.97	5.48	5.54
4.50	25	7.02	5.60	5.61
4.50	25	7.08	5.64	5.69
3.00	30	6.18	4.56	4.55
3.00	30	6.40	5.35	5.41
4.00	30	6.55	5.92	5.89
4.00	30	6.65	6.00	6.17
4.50	30	6.78	6.56	6.48
4.50	30	6.90	6.60	6.71
4.50	30	7.00	6.80	6.89
4.50	30	7.08	6.92	7.01
5.20	35	6.24	5.40	5.39
5.20	35	6.40	6.41	6.21
5.20	35	6.55	6.60	6.85
4.50	35	6.70	7.55	7.42
4.50	35	6.81	7.86	7.78
4.50	35	6.90	8.12	8.03
4.50	35	7.04	8.20	8.38
4.50	35	7.13	8.71	8.58

The structure of the zwitterionic form of α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid can be represented as

According to this structure Co^{II} may attack at three positions, (i) indole nitrogen, (ii) side chain nitrogen and (iii) oxygen of the carboxylate group. But Weber and Simeon^{1,4} in their chelation study of metal ion with α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid have shown that indole nitrogen does not take part in the chelation. This was further confirmed from the formation constants^{1,6} of Co^{II} with α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid. Therefore, α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid could be treated as bidentate ligand.

It is known from the literature^{1,2} that in case of bidentate ligand, only monoprotonated (which is changed into deprotonated form) is generally considered for the reactions. Zwitterionic form of α -

amino- β -indolepropionic acid can exist in the following dissociation equilibria,

Thus it is obvious that α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid can be treated as bidentate ligand. The diprotonated (H_2L^+), monoprotonated (HL) and deprotonated (L^-) forms of α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid can react in the following way,

Then it can be shown that²

$$k_{\text{obs}} \cdot \frac{\{K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2 + [\text{H}^+]^2\}}{K_1[\text{H}^+]} = k_1 + \frac{k_2K_2}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (5)$$

This rate law can be reconciled in terms of stepwise scheme as represented in equation (6),

In the previous studies^{1,2}, only one dissociation constant corresponding to NH_3 group was taken into consideration for the bidentate ligand. We have, however, taken into account both the dissociation constants corresponding to NH_3 and COOH groups and obtained a rate equation which is slightly different from others²,

$$k_{\text{obs}} \cdot \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2}{K_1[\text{H}^+]} = \frac{k_{12}k_{23}k_{34}K_1[\text{H}^+] + k_{23}k_{34}k_{45}K_1K_2}{k_{23}k_{34}[\text{H}^+] + k_{34}(k_{34} + k_{35})} \quad (7)$$

which on approximation $k_{23}k_{34}[\text{H}^+] \ll k_{34}(k_{34} + k_{35})$ leads to

$$k_{\text{obs}} \cdot \frac{K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2 + [\text{H}^+]^2}{K_1[\text{H}^+]} = \frac{k_{12}k_{35}}{k_{34} + k_{35}} + \frac{k_{45}k_{35}}{k_{34} + k_{35}} \times \frac{K_2}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) is similar to equation (5) if $k_1 = k_{12}k_{23}/k_{34} + k_{23}$ and $k_2 = k_{43}k_{35}/k_{34} + k_{23}$. Plots of $k_{obs} \{K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2 + [H^+]^2\}/K_1[H^+]$ vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ at 25, 30 and 35 $\pm 0.05^\circ$ are shown in Fig. 1 which are non-linear curves. The values of K_1 and K_2 at 25 $^\circ$ have been taken from literature¹⁶ and these values were corrected for 30 and 35 $^\circ$ using the relation,

$$pK_a = \frac{\Delta H_a(T_2 - T_1)}{4.576 T_2 T_1} + pK_a^{25^\circ}$$

It is noticed that curves are non-linear in high pH region, indicating that cobalt(II) - α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid chelation cannot be explained by equations (5) and (8). Therefore, it is necessary to consider other suitable schemes which could explain non-linearity of the curves in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Variation of $k_{obs} \{[H^+]^2 + K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2\}/K_1[H^+]$ vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ for the reaction of Co^{II} with α -amino- β -indolepropionic acid.

It is known from the literature^{11,12} that such problems may be overcome by the detailed examination of chelation process. A new scheme is given below,

The rate of the reaction can thus be written as

$$\text{Rate} = k_{23}[\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{Co}] + k_{65}[\text{Co}-\text{N}-\text{O}] \quad (10)$$

Now using steady-state approximation for non-chelated species $[\text{HN}^+-\text{O}-\text{Co}]$, $[\text{Co}-\text{N}-\text{O}]$ and $[\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{Co}]$, it can be shown that

$$[\text{Co}-\text{N}-\text{O}] = \frac{k_{46}[\text{N}-\text{O}^-][\text{Co}^{2+}]}{k_{64} + k_{65}} \quad (11)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 &[\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{Co}] \\
 &= \frac{(k_{23} + k_{25})k_{43}[\text{N}-\text{O}^-][\text{Co}^{2+}] + k_{23}k_{12}[\text{HN}^+-\text{O}^-]}{(k_{34} + k_{35})(k_{21} + k_{23}) + k_{21}k_{23}[\text{H}^+]} \quad (12)
 \end{aligned}$$

After substituting the value of $[\text{N}-\text{O}^-]$ and $[\text{HN}^+-\text{O}^-]$ in terms of $[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}]$, we get equations (13) and (14).

$$[\text{Co}-\text{N}-\text{O}] = \frac{k_{46}K_1K_2[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}][\text{Co}^{2+}]}{[\text{H}^+]^2(k_{64} + k_{65})} \quad (13)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 &[\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{Co}] = \frac{(k_{23} + k_{25})k_{43}K_1K_2 + k_{23}k_{12}K_1[\text{H}^+]}{(k_{34} + k_{35})(k_{21} + k_{23}) + k_{21}k_{23}[\text{H}^+]} \\
 &\quad \frac{[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}][\text{Co}^{2+}]}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (14)
 \end{aligned}$$

On putting these values of $[\text{Co}-\text{N}-\text{O}]$ and $[\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{Co}]$ in equation (10), the rate law becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Rate} = &\left[\frac{k_{23}(k_{21} + k_{25})k_{43}K_1K_2 + k_{23}k_{12}K_1[\text{H}^+]}{(k_{34} + k_{35})(k_{21} + k_{23}) + k_{21}k_{23}[\text{H}^+]} \right. \\
 &\left. + \frac{k_{46}k_{65}K_1K_2}{k_{64} + k_{65}} \right] \times \frac{[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}][\text{Co}^{2+}]}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (15)
 \end{aligned}$$

In scheme (9) both k_{21} and k_{23} are first order constants and the overall reaction goes to completion. Therefore, $k_{23} \gg k_{21}$. Assuming⁶ that $k_{65} > k_{64}$ and $k_{35} > k_{34}$, and after rearrangement, equation (15) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Rate} = &\frac{k_{43}K_1K_2 + k_{12}K_1[\text{H}^+] + k_{46}K_1K_2 + \frac{k_{46}K_1K_2k_{21}k_{23}[\text{H}^+]}{k_{23}k_{25}}}{\{1 + k_{21}k_{23}[\text{H}^+]/k_{23}k_{25}\}} \\
 &\times \frac{[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}][\text{Co}^{2+}]}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (16)
 \end{aligned}$$

Since the product K_1K_2 is very small and also k_{23} and k_{25} are very large, therefore, 4th term in equation (16) will be negligible and can be ignored under our experimental conditions. Therefore, equation (17) is final form of the rate equation,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Rate} = &\frac{(k_{43} + k_{46})K_1K_2 + k_{12}K_1[\text{H}^+]}{\{1 + k_{21}k_{23}[\text{H}^+]/k_{23}k_{25}\}} \\
 &\times \frac{[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}][\text{Co}^{2+}]}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (17)
 \end{aligned}$$

Rate from equation (1) in terms of $[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}]$ can also be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Rate} = &k_{obs} \{K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2 + [\text{H}^+]^2\} \\
 &\frac{[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}][\text{Co}^{2+}]}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (18)
 \end{aligned}$$

TABLE 2—VALUES OF A, B AND C

Temp. °C	A × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	B × 10 ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	C × 10 ⁻⁶ mol ⁻¹
25	1.08 ± 0.26	6.10 ± 2.65	1.05 ± 0.43
30	1.61 ± 0.39	7.44 ± 3.23	0.95 ± 0.46
35	2.44 ± 0.56	9.12 ± 3.85	1.20 ± 0.52

TABLE 3—VALUES OF (k_{4s} + k_{4e}), k_{1s} AND k_{4s}k_{3s}/k_{3s}k_{4s}

Temp. °C	(k _{4s} + k _{4e}) × 10 ⁻⁴ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	k _{1s} × 10 ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	(k _{4s} k _{3s} /k _{3s} k _{4s}) × 10 ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
25	2.15	6.10	1.22
30	2.50	7.44	1.21
35	2.85	9.12	0.89

TABLE 4—VALUES OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS CORRESPONDING TO (k_{4s} + k_{4e}) AND k_{1s}

ΔH _{1s} [‡] kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔE _{1s} [‡] kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS _{1s} [‡] cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH _{4s+4e} [‡] kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔE _{4s+4e} [‡] kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS _{4s+4e} [‡] cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
6.86	7.63	-22.20	4.58	5.23	-27.34

On comparing equations (17) and (18), we get equation (19),

$$k_{obs} = \frac{(k_{4s} + k_{4e})K_2 + k_{1s}[H^+]}{(1 + k_{21}k_{3s}[H^+]/k_{3s}k_{2s})} \frac{K_1}{[H^+]^2 + K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2} \quad (19)$$

Equation (19) can also be arranged in the form of equation (20),

$$k_{obs} = \frac{A + B[H^+]}{C[H^+] + 1} \frac{K_1}{[H^+]^2 + K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2} \quad (20)$$

where, A = (k_{4s} + k_{4e})K₂, B = k_{1s} and C = k₂₁k_{3s}/k_{3s}k_{2s}.

In order to calculate the values of A, B and C, a non-linear least-square analysis was used. The values of A, B and C at 25, 30 and 35 ± 0.05° are given in Table 2.

From the scheme represented by equation (9), we can write

$$K_1' = \frac{k_{2s}}{k_{21}} = \frac{[N-O-Co][H^+]}{[HN^+-O-Co]}$$

Therefore, C can be written as

$$C = k_{21}/K_1'k_{3s} \quad (21)$$

But it is known from literature⁴ and also clear from equation (9) that

$$k_{4s}/k_{3s} = k_{1s}K_1'/k_{21}K_2 \quad (22)$$

From equations (21) and (22),

$$C = k_{1s}k_{3s}/K_2k_{4s}k_{3s} \quad (23)$$

On substituting the values of C, k_{1s} and K₂ in equation (23), we obtain the value of k_{4s}k_{3s}/k_{3s}k_{4s}. The values of different specific rate constants at 25, 30 and 35 ± 0.05° are presented in Table 3.

Now it is difficult to mention whether k_{4s} or k_{4e} is larger (Table 3). But from the scheme in equation (9), it can be predicted that k_{4s} has a larger value than k_{4e} due to strong electrostatic attraction between negatively charged oxygen and positively charged cobalt ion.

Values of activation parameters corresponding to specific rate constants (k_{4s} + k_{4e}) and k_{1s} are given in Table 4. The experimental and calculated

values of second order rate constants (k_{obs}) are in good agreement (Table 1).

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